

Original Research

Performance Based Skills Gap Analysis in Tanzanian Small Scale Manufacturing Firms

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Abstract

The performance of small firms, particularly those engaged in small-scale manufacturing, is a critical issue not only in Tanzania but throughout the world. This study analyzed the skills gap and how it affects the performance of small-scale manufacturing sector in Mwanza and Dar es Salaam cities in Tanzania. Gathering of quantitative data was performed under usage of a standardized questionnaire from 175 randomly selected small-business owner and employed managers. The analysis of data was aided using tools for analysis known as Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Ms. Excel whereas descriptive statistics in form of percent, frequency and means scores were computed. Further, crosstab to establish how variables are associated was achieved by performing Chi-Square. Skills gaps were established by taking the difference of mean scores between employers' perceptions (P) and expectations (E). Determination of skills gap on SSMFs' performance was achieved using Logit model. The findings indicated that the skills gap exists with an overall mean score of -0.7302. The findings further exhibited that skills gaps including technical, communication, problem solving, interpersonal and decision making statistically were significant with negative relationships ($p < 0.05$). The recommendations made include policymakers, development partners and owners of SSMFs to collaborate in closing identified skills gaps by designing training programmes with sufficient budgets being set aside for the training sessions.

Keywords: Firms' performance, skills gap, small scale manufacturing firms, Tanzania.

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Introduction

The terms skills gap is meant to address the degree to which employees miss the required skills to fulfil their job requirements (Sallwa, 2023; NACTE, 2020). The focus of this research conceptualized skills gap as any difference that exists between the expectations of employers and perceptions of employers. Studies about skills gap in the world including Tanzania across various sectors and industries have become popular. For example, the study of Shivaramu *et al.* (2019) found existence of skills gap among workforce in Sanria Engineering Pvt Limited in India. The study further established that decision making skills, interpersonal skills, problem solving skills and communication skills had impact on the performance of workforce except technical skills that demonstrated insignificant impact.

The term manufacturing is conceptualized as transformation of raw materials as in puts into usable products that provide value (MIT, 2014). The typical firms notable in manufacturing sector just to list a few in Tanzania are those concerning with woodworking, leather, textiles, light machinery, metalworking, agro-processing, chemicals and fertilizers (MIT, 2014). The industry that turns agricultural and all other non-agricultural raw materials into products and adds value to them is referred to in this study as the manufacturing sector. According to URT (2003), small-scale manufacturing firms can be matched with small and medium enterprises i.e. micro scale manufacturing enterprises are those with 1-4 employees and invested up to TZS 5 million capital investment. Small enterprises are those manufacturing firms with 5-49 employees and invested capital between TZS 5 and 200 million. Medium-scale manufacturing firms are those with 50 to 99 employees with invested capital in a range of TZS 200 and 800 million.

The global manufacturing growth rate was reported to be 0.1% in the first quarter of 2024, this growth rate was spelt out as inactive performance in the manufacturing sector (UNIDO, 2024a). Countrywide globally, manufacturing growth rate was counted as China being the leading country in manufacturing rate with 1.3% in the first quarter, this accounts for approximately to 12% of the overall global manufacturing growth rate (UNIDO, 2024a). Other countries globally in top five with manufacturing growth rates in brackets, USA (-0.1%), Japan (-5.2%), Germany (0.8%) and the Republic of Korea (-0.6%) (UNIDO, 2024). The most presented reason for the global manufacturing growth rate is intensity in technological growth such as electronics, computers and use of artificial intelligence (UNIDO, 2024a; UNIDO, 2024b). The interpretation from the fact presented is that though the major driver for such manufacturing growth rate is pointed out as technological advancement, investment in human capital that innovate and operate technological machines is the cornerstone in this agendum. In the USA, the manufacturing sector contributed to the GDP USD 2.9 trillion which is equivalent to greater than 10% of the total output economically (ING, 2024). The report further informed that 8.3% of employment in USA come from manufacturing sector (ING, 2024). The contribution of manufacturing sector to GDP and employment in USA provides evidence that the sector is crucial and prioritization to the sector is something to be integrated in the global agenda. In the European Union, the contribution of the sector responsible with manufacturing was 25% of the net turnover in business economy in

European Union in 2020 and it is one of the large employers employing 30 million people in 2021 in the European Union (Eurostat, 2024). Such a contribution in the economy and employment of the sector responsible with manufacturing provides evidence that the sector is important in the global economy.

In African countries, the sector in manufacturing overrepresented by increasing number of informal and small firms with high employment growth rate that increased from 0.6% in 1990 to 9% in 2018, though the sector is characterized with high number of low skilled workforce (African Economic Outlook, 2024). In a similar way in South Africa, manufacturing sector has demonstrated production growth with an increase of 2.6% in January 2024 as compared with that of the same month in 2023 and increased by 0.8% in January 2024 in comparison to that of December 2023, such growth in manufacturing production corresponds with increased employment rate. In Kenya for instance, the exports have increased by 6% from 35% in 2018 to 41% in 2022, manufacturing sector being pronounced as the main contributor (Kenya Association of Manufacturers, 2024). The report further informs that, in 2030, the Kenyan contribution to GDP from manufacturing sector is forecasted to be 20%, to achieve this projection investment in human capital is one of the strategies (Kenya Association of Manufacturers, 2024). The projection of 20% as contribution to GDP from manufacturing sector in Kenya has come in plans but currently Kenya has experienced a drop of 3,28% in the contribution of manufacturing sector to GDP from 11.08% in 2011 to 7.8% in 2022 (Kenya Association of Manufacturers, 2024). Such a drop in the contribution to GDP is an alarm that the manufacturing sector is being confronted with some specific challenges, amongst which is inadequate investment in human capital. The sector has contributed to increase of 2.59% in employment in Kenya from 343,700 jobs in 2017 to 352,600 jobs in 2022 (Kenya Association of Manufacturers, 2024). The increase in contribution to employment from manufacturing sector indicates that the sector is crucial despite the challenges confronting the sector.

In Tanzania, the growth of manufacturing sector has remained almost the same for the period of two decades (Klinger *et al.*, 2023), with 8.2% contribution to the GDP and employing 8% of total employment in 2021 (Embassy of Switzerland in Tanzania, 2024), implying that there is a lot to be done to accelerate growth of manufacturing sector in Tanzania. The study of Diao *et al.* (2021) came up, with similar findings that indicated that Tanzanian firms dealing with manufacturing have demonstrated stunted growth in terms of productivity and employment, the causes cite among others is limited technologies with limited workforce to operate and make use of such technologies. In the view of this, firms dealing with manufacturing in Tanzania have largely focused to invest in financial capital but less has been integrated in practice in terms of human resources' competences. Tanzanian small-scale manufacturing firms are constrained with low survival problems and poor performance (Mashenene and Kumburu, 2020; Magasi, 2020). The most cited reason for such low survival rate and performance of the SSMFs in Tanzania is the human factor in terms of shortage of skills and capacity (Mashenene and Kumburu, 2020; Magasi, 2020; Mashenene, 2018).

Higher education institutions' production and the demand of the labour market are out of sync because of inadequate or out-of-date curricula that have no direct connections to industry (Munishi, 2016). The World Bank Group (2024) in Tanzania has indicated that

the prospect for industrial sector to expand has experienced slow rate it decreased from 5.7% growth rate in 2022 to 5.2% in 2023, making a decline of 8.8%, the decline which is substantial and posing unanswered questions. The same report further pointed out that the likelihood cause for the unpromising growth rate in industrial sector is the result of rapid increase in population, almost doubling in every 23 years, this makes difficulty for the country to thoroughly invest and develop well skilled human capital (World Bank Group, 2024). Inadequacy in building human capital has resulted in skills gap in the labour market whereas employees experience limited soft skills to enable them to perform the required jobs appropriately as it was rated by more than 60% of employers (NACTE, 2020). The commonly soft skills that employers identified to be missing from their employees were problem solving, language, writing, communication, teamwork, customer care, innovation, report writing and IT related skills. As the situation was empirically evidenced by employers in the labour market in Tanzania, employers counting to 39% of expressed that workforce were not able to make application of the knowledge they have to perform related jobs whereas employers counting to 26% expressed that employees had passed through training with obsolete technologies (NACTE, 2020).

The Tanzania government and other development partners have developed some mechanisms to address such skills gap among employees in the labour market. Such mechanisms include designing of competence based curricula being regulated by NACTVET (NACTE, 2020), establishment of vocational training institutions (NACTE, 2020), increased secondary schools and higher learning institutions (NACTE, 2020), development of the National Five Year Development Plan 2021/2022 – 2025/2026 (United Republic of Tanzania, 2021) and others but still the skills gap among employees in the labour market is still reported to exist (World Bank Group, 2024; NACTE, 2020; Mashenene and Kumburu, 2020; Munishi, 2016). The study hence carried out performance-based skills gap analysis in SSMFs in Tanzania. Specifically, the study dealt with; (i) assessment of the existence of skills gap among owner and employed managers in SSMFs in Tanzania, (ii) examining the determinants of skills gap for SSMFs in Tanzania and (iii) establishment of the effect of skills gap on the performance of SSMFs in Tanzania. The study attempted the following research questions; (i) What specific skills gap exists among owner and employed managers in Tanzanian SSMFs? (ii) What are the determinants of the identified skills gap among owner and employed managers for SSMFs in Tanzania? (iii) To what extent does identified skills gap affects the performance of SSMFs in Tanzania?

Theoretical Framework

Barney formed the Resource Based Theory (RBT) in 1986, which maintains that a company's internal resources and competencies provide it with the greatest edge over other companies in the market (Kay, 2007). According to the notion, a firm is a collection of assets or capabilities, and a corporation's ability to succeed depends on its unique skills. In this study, human resources with appropriate skills in the SSMFs are valuable assets and capabilities that give such firms the ability to exploit emerging business opportunities in the sector. Human resources as human capital is a valuable internal resource for the firms, as they have relevant skills for firms' operations, they become important internal assets that give competitive advantage to the firms. The potentiality of human resources

being an important asset falls under the competences possessed by such human resources (Mashenene and Kumburu, 2020). The study of Mashenene and Kumburu (2020) discovered that human resources' competencies, commitment and honesty were key ingredients in the aspect of human resource as the firms' asset with high value. It is from this study that focused on human resource-based view instead of addressing resources based in general, the study supports the resource-based theory. The competencies that were integrated in the study of Mashenene and Kumburu (2020) important skills possessed by firms' staff such as technical skills, problems solving skills, communication skills, interpersonal skills and decision-making skills. The study further pointed out that in some circumstances where firms' fail to attract or retain staff with the required competencies, then they lose important assets that will make them fail to attain the desired goals. The skills focused on this study are technical skills, communication skills, problem solving skills, interpersonal skills and decision making. Therefore, in the circumstance where these skills are not possessed by the firms' staff, then skills gap is formed, which is the degree at which employees miss the required skills to execute the job that they employed for (Sallwa, 2023; NACTE, 2020).

Empirical Literature Review

In the global perspective, China is the leading country in manufacturing productivity with 31.6% of the manufacturing output globally followed by the USA with 15.9% whereas Japan being the third leading country with output from manufacturing sector of 6.5% followed by German with 4.8% and the India being the least top in top five leading countries in the world with 2.9% of manufacturing outputs (Safeguard Global, 2024). These findings inform that manufacturing sector is vital in the global economy as it positions countries which have heavily invested in the sector in higher economic ranks. In China, Yan (2024) pointed out that during the first quarter of 2024 the outputs from the sector involved in manufacturing increased by 6.1% in comparison to the same quarter of the last year and the employment in the sector seemed to be continuously improving, this growth is remarkable and it is one of the economic indicators that positions China as one of the top countries in economic growth globally. The drivers cited for this remarkable economic growth are huge investment in high tech and human resources in the manufacturing sector through research and development during the period from 2012 to 2021 that China has made (Yan, 2024). In the USA, the productivity from the sector involved in manufacturing grew by 1.3% in quarter two of 2024 in comparison to quarter two of 2023, this resulted in an increase in employment and consequently productivity of labour increased by 1.6% in quarter two of 2024 in comparison to the corresponding quarter of 2023 (US Bureau of Labour Statistics, 2024). The most cited reasons for this growth include technological advancement and huge investment in human resources including developing relevant management skills (US Bureau of Labour Statistics, 2024). These findings provide a basis for interpretation that investment in technology and human resources is inevitable for the country that wishes to bring positive changes in the sector responsible for manufacturing.

In Africa, the African Futures and Innovation Programme (2024) indicated that the share of the sector concerning manufacturing in Africa generally decreased by 5% from 18% to 13%, however, it is projected to experience growth by 22% in 2043. In a similar manner, in Sub-Saharan Africa the GDP emanating from the sector concerning with

manufacturing has remained nearly constant from 2000 to 2020 (African Futures and Innovation Programme, 2024). In contrast to Western countries, the contribution of the sector concerning manufacturing experienced growth, the most cited causes are heavy investment in technology and human resources. In Nigeria, the study of Ogar *et al.* (2024) that investigated how employment is impacted by manufacturing firms came up with the findings that depict that enhancing manufacturing sector is one of important strategic decision the country would prioritize, meaning that the country that intends to foster employment rate in the country should among other sectors consider manufacturing as one of them. The study of Ngepah *et al.* (2024) in South Africa came up with recommendations that the sector concerning with manufacturing requires extensive investment in ICT and advanced education, meaning that well educated workforce is required to cope with the dynamic technological changes. The study of Ogunjobi *et al.* (2022) indicated that the quality and quantity of workforce in the labour market in Nigeria statistically do not demonstrate positive contribution, giving connotation that skills gap and limited number of workforces exist in the labour market. The situation in South Africa was similarly experienced whereas production in the sector responsible with production declined by 6.4% during the period of March 2023 in comparison to March of the previous year (Republic of South Africa, 2024), this provides implication that the sector's contribution to economic growth is at the declining rate.

In Tanzania, the country experienced an increase in total exports from manufacturing by 23% in the period between 2011 and 2015, in contrast, in the period between 2011 and 2020 the country experienced decline in in total exports from manufacturing by 29% (Guliev and Mehari, 2023). The main causes pronounced for the decline in total exports emanating from manufacturing in Tanzania is the failure to meet the lowest human resources requirements in terms of skills required, implying that investing in human resources to attain required competences is crucial to help restore exports in manufacturing sector. The sector concerning manufacturing is confronted with various challenges, amongst inadequate skilled human resources on quality of 4.0 technologies and their applications in manufacturing (Maganga and Taifa, 2023), implying that technological advancement is required to be in parallel with investment in developing labour which is the cornerstone for the manufacturing process. The study of Diao *et al.* (2021) established that Tanzanian manufacturing firms under perform with meagre growth in productivity with limited expansion in employment rate. The most cited driving factor for this situation is existence of skills shortage among workforce in the labour market.

Research Methods

Research design

This research made use of a cross-sectional research design which permitted gathering of data at once during the process of gathering data to allow objectivity in analysis and conclusion without considering the history or trend of the phenomenon under study (Pallant, 2016). This research design has been applicable in many past studies since it is cost effective and time conscious (Mashenene and Kumburu, 2020; Magasi, 2020).

Sampling

The research took place in Mwanza and Dar es Salaam cities since the cities contain over 50% of all manufacturing firms in Tanzania (Magasi, 2020). The population of the study was 10,142 owners and employed managers in manufacturing firms. The study selected a sample of 175 owners and employed managers using a formula of Green (1991). The computation of sample size using Green formula (1991) was presented using the equation $N > 50 + 8m$, whereas N = sample size and m = number of predictors involved in the study. Since the study has five predictors, this resulted into $N > 50 + 8 \times 5 = N > 90$, inferring that the sample size was supposed to be 90. However, Anders *et al.* (2017) employed a sample size of 155 instead of 82 that was computed using Green formula (1991) with 4 predictors. Further, instead of using 66 sample size that was computed using Green formula (1991), Magasi (2021) used a sample size of 131. The sample sizes used in the studies of Anders *et al.* (2017) and Magasi (2021) seemed to double from the sample sizes computed using Green formula (1991). It is from this derivation, the sample size for this study was 175 which also seemed to double from the computed sample size (Magasi, 2021; Anders *et al.*, 2017). Two stage sampling procedures were considered in selecting the owner and employed managers from manufacturing firms. In the beginning, regions were purposefully selected due to having the largest number of small-scale manufacturing firms. Using lists obtained from street leaders, owners and employed managers were randomly selected.

Data collection

A questionnaire containing questions in closed ended fashion was used in collecting quantitative data. Formulation of questions in a questionnaire were adopted and modified from NACTE (2020) and Shivaramu *et al.* (2019). Capturing of the required skills to measure the gap; technical skills (five statements), communication skills (two statements), problem solving skills (five statements), interpersonal skills (two statements) and decision skills (two statements) was performed using questions with a 5-point Likert scale (1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree). The questions aimed at measuring skills gap were developed in duplicate pairs with equal number of corresponding questions for perceptions (P) and expectations (E) (Shivaramu *et al.*, 2019). Data for measuring determinants of skills gap were obtained using questions with 5 points Likert scale style with 10 statements. To capture the performance of manufacturing firms under the study, eight statements with Likert scale questions were developed. The age of respondents was captured in years, sex was a dummy variable (1=male, 2= female), education level was captured using the number of years spent in education, experience in business was years spent by managers in management. Training to data collectors as assistants to researchers was undertaken to make them familiar with the tool for collecting data, this was aimed at enhancing data validity.

Data analysis and analytical model

The Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 23 was used as a tool for analyzing quantitative data. Descriptive statistics were performed whereas demographic characteristics of respondents were presented in form of frequency, percent and mean. Since the research was concerned with skills gap, demographic characteristics of

respondents underwent crosstabulation to establish Chi-Square value which is a measure of association between variables under the measurement. Only demographic characteristics which were found statistically significant were presented and it necessitated computation of coefficients of Phi and Crammer's V for determination of size of the effect (Pallant, 2016; Cohen, 1988). The coefficients of Phi and Crammer's V are presented from 0 to 1 whereas those with higher values connote large size of the effect. Cohen (1988) interpreted the coefficients with 0.1 = small size of the effect, 0.30 = medium size of the effect and 0.5 = large size of the effect. The analysis of skills gap was serially performed by first computing mean scores for both perception and expectations. Secondly, the computed mean scores were involved in computing the difference between perception (P) and expectations (E), P – E (Shivaramu *et al.*, 2019). Thirdly, ranking of the computed mean score for each skills gap was carried out to establish ranks that helped in predicting the magnitude of the gaps. Finally, summation of all the differences obtained (skills gap) was performed and the total was divided by five (number of skills gaps measured) to obtain the overall skills gap. The analysis for determinants of skills gap was carried out by first computing mean score of each determinant that was followed by computation of the overall mean score that was used in gauging and comparing mean scores of the variables to enable establishment of decision criteria for mean scores below or above the overall mean score. Only determinants whose skills gap with mean scores was above the overall mean scores were discussed in the study, otherwise they were not considered for the discussion.

Further analysis was performed using logit model, an econometric model applicable when dependent variable is categorical (1= if performance rose above the mean score, 0= if performance remained below the mean score). For independent variables an exploratory factor analysis, commonly known as principal factor analysis (PCA) was carried out aiming at exploring how variables are interrelated and also for reducing several variables into fewer variables which are easy to manage. In this research, 16 variables initially present were reduced into five variables in groups of technical skills gap, communication skills gap, problem solving skills gap, interpersonal skills gap and decision-making skills gap. Mashenene (2016) and Bengesi (2013) applied exploratory factor analysis in establishing how variables were interrelated among themselves and lowered them into fewer ones. The relevance of PCA was projected by the Kaiser-Mayer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test of sphericity. The value for KMO always is in a range from 0 to 1, with a value of 0 being defined as a factor which is unfitting. The value of KMO nearby 1, is understood as the forms of variables with dense correlations resulting into formation of reliable and unique factors (Field, 2013). According to Kaiser (1974), clarification of values for KMO with scores higher than 0.5 are defined as satisfactory, values less than 0.5 require researchers to collect supplementary information for the research. Clarification of KMO values in the range of 0.5 - 0.7 is well-defined as average, good for 0.7 - 0.8, great for 0.8 - 0.9 and outstanding for above 0.9. The logit model was used to quantify the influence of skills gap on the SSMFs' performance. The following equation is used to present the binary logistic regression model:

$$\left(Y = \frac{1}{X_s} \right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T e_1 + \beta_2 P s_2 + \beta_3 I p_3 + \beta_4 D m_4 + \beta_5 A g_5 + \beta_6 S e_6 + \varepsilon_i \dots \dots \dots (4)$$

Whereby:

Y= SSMFs' performance which is the dependent variable, Te = Technical skills gap, Ps = Problem solving skills gap, Ip = Interpersonal skills gap, Dm = Decision making skills gap, Ag = Age, SE=Sex and β_0 = Model estimation for coefficients.

Findings and Discussion

KMO and Bartlett's Test

The KMO results in Table 1 indicate the value of 0.865, indicating that data were appropriate for factor analysis (Field, 2013). The null hypothesis that the initial correlation matrix is the matrix for identity matrix which is measured by Bartlett's test of sphericity. The researcher must create some associations between variables for factor analysis to be appropriate; for the R-matrix to be matrix for identity, then all coefficients of correlation would be 0, in this view, such a coefficient always is significant in this sense. The presence of a significant test suggests that the R-matrix is not matrix for identity, implying the existence of some links among the variables analyzed, thus, factor analysis was proper in this research, as indicated by the extremely significant results of Bartlett's test ($p < 0.001$) (Nyange *et al.*, 2016; Mashenene, 2016).

Table 1. Bartlett's Test and KMO

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Sampling Adequacy Measure		0.865
Bartlett's Sphericity Test	Approx. Chi-Square	1261.540
	df	120
	Sig.	0.000

Sample Characteristics

Age of Respondents

Distribution of respondents' age was presented in Table 2. The results indicated that the mean age of respondents was 36.6 years, implying that this age is for youth. Equivalently, groupwise the results indicate that 91.5% of respondents had the age ranging between 18 to 45 years, the age group of youth, energetic and productive. These results are similar to those of Mashenene and Kumburu (2020) which established that owners of small businesses in Tanzania had an age mean of 35.5 years, the age of youth.

Sex of respondents

Table 2 indicates that the majority of owner and employed managers were male (65.7%) compared to their counterpart female (34.3%), implying that such kind of business is dominated by male. Similar results were established in Mashenene (2020) in which male overrepresented female in business ownership.

Education level

Table 2 shows that the majority (78.3%) of owner and employed managers had college/university education whereas only 5.7% had primary education and 16.0%

secondary education. The implication of these results is that the majority of business owners have entrusted their businesses to managers whose level of education matches managerial level.

Table 2. Sample Characteristics (n = 175)

Variables	Frequency	Percent
<i>Age (years)</i>		
18-30	43	24.6
31-45	117	66.9
46-55	12	6.9
56-75	3	1.7
Total	175	100.0
Mean age [Std. Dev.]	36.6 [7.77]	
Min., Max. [Range]	22, 68 [46]	
<i>Sex</i>		
Female	60	34.3
Male	115	65.7
Total	175	100.0
<i>Education level</i>		
Primary	10	5.7
Secondary	28	16.0
Certificate	22	12.6
Diploma	21	12.0
Degree	94	53.7
Total	175	100.0
<i>Business type</i>		
Textile/Garments	25	14.3
Food/Beverage	76	43.4
Furniture	25	14.3
Metal	24	13.7
Chemical	9	5.1
Others	16	9.1
Total	175	100.0
<i>Business experience (years)</i>		
1-3	56	32.0
4-6	63	36.0
7-10	38	21.7
11+	18	10.3
Total	175	100.0
Mean experience [Std. Dev.]	5.98 [4.55]	
Min., Max. [Range]	1, 22 [21]	

Business experience

The results in Table 2 reveal that the mean score of business experience for owner and employed managers was 5.98 years, implying that such managers were experienced enough to perform managerial duties in their businesses.

Crosstabulation Results

Age categories and experience categories crosstabulation

Table 3. Age categories and experience categories crosstabulation

Age categories	Percent	Experience categories (years)				Total
		1-3	4-6	7-10	11+	
18-30 years	Count	24	19	0	0	43
	% within Age categories	55.8%	44.2%	0.0%	0.0%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	42.9%	30.2%	0.0%	0.0%	24.7%
	% of Total	13.8%	10.9%	0.0%	0.0%	24.7%
31-45 years	Count	32	41	33	10	116
	% within Age categories	27.6%	35.3%	28.4%	8.6%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	57.1%	65.1%	86.8%	58.8%	66.7%
	% of Total	18.4%	23.6%	19.0%	5.7%	66.7%
46-55 years	Count	0	3	3	6	12
	% within Age categories	0.0%	25.0%	25.0%	50.0%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	0.0%	4.8%	7.9%	35.3%	6.9%
	% of Total	0.0%	1.7%	1.7%	3.4%	6.9%
56-75 years	Count	0	0	2	1	3
	% within Age categories	0.0%	0.0%	66.7%	33.3%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	0.0%	0.0%	5.3%	5.9%	1.7%
	% of Total	0.0%	0.0%	1.1%	0.6%	1.7%
Total	Count	56	63	38	17	174
	% within Age categories	32.2%	36.2%	21.8%	9.8%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	32.2%	36.2%	21.8%	9.8%	100.0%

(Pearson Chi-Square (χ^2) value =55.800, df=9, p=0.000), Phi=0.566, Cramer's V=0.327)

The findings in Table 3 indicate that the highest age group of 31-45 years consisted of 66.7% followed by that of 18-30 with 24.7% making a total of 91.4%, informing that both age groups of 18-30 and 31-45 years are the age groups of youth which is a productive age given the fact that they have several family responsibilities, meaning that they need business skills to enable them perform well their businesses. The findings further on crosstab between age groups and experience in business indicated association between them which is statistically significant [$\chi^2 = 55.800, p = 0.009$] with a medium effect size between them as measured by the coefficient of Cramer's $V=0.327$ (Cohen, 1988). The implication in these findings inform that the association that exist between age groups of respondents and business experience existed with medium size of the effect, meaning that both parameters age group being age of youth and business 3xperience were important ingredients in business performance.

Education and experience categories crosstabulation

The findings in Table 4 indicate that a total of 78.1% of selected business managers had tertiary education level whereas the highest number being 53.4% with degree followed by 12.6% with certificate and 12.1% with diploma, signifying that such managers had adequate formal education to enable them carry out their businesses with high expectations to reach desired business performance. The findings on crosstab between education and experience in business indicate a statistically significant association [$\chi^2 =33.268, df =12, p=0.001$] with small size effect as represented by the coefficient of Cramer's $V=0.252$ (Cohen, 1988). These findings give reflection that the selected managers in the study were experienced in business and had satisfactory level of education to enable them to undertake their business projects to the desired performance.

Table 4. Education and experience categories crosstabulation

Education level	Percent	Experience categories				Total
		1-3	4-6	7-10	11+	
Primary	Count	4	4	0	2	10
	% within EDUCATION	40.0%	40.0%	0.0%	20.0%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	7.1%	6.3%	0.0%	11.8%	5.7%
	% of Total	2.3%	2.3%	0.0%	1.1%	5.7%
Secondary	Count	6	9	12	1	28
	% within EDUCATION	21.4%	32.1%	42.9%	3.6%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	10.7%	14.3%	31.6%	5.9%	16.1%
	% of Total	3.4%	5.2%	6.9%	0.6%	16.1%
Certificate	Count	8	5	2	7	22
	% within EDUCATION	36.4%	22.7%	9.1%	31.8%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	14.3%	7.9%	5.3%	41.2%	12.6%
	% of Total	4.6%	2.9%	1.1%	4.0%	12.6%
Diploma	Count	4	8	5	4	21
	% within EDUCATION	19.0%	38.1%	23.8%	19.0%	100.0%

Education level	Percent	Experience categories				Total
		1-3	4-6	7-10	11+	
	% within Experience categories	7.1%	12.7%	13.2%	23.5%	12.1%
	% of Total	2.3%	4.6%	2.9%	2.3%	12.1%
Degree	Count	34	37	19	3	93
	% within EDUCATION	36.6%	39.8%	20.4%	3.2%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	60.7%	58.7%	50.0%	17.6%	53.4%
	% of Total	19.5%	21.3%	10.9%	1.7%	53.4%
Total	Count	56	63	38	17	174
	% within EDUCATION	32.2%	36.2%	21.8%	9.8%	100.0%
	% within Experience categories	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%
	% of Total	32.2%	36.2%	21.8%	9.8%	100.0%

(Pearson Chi-Square (χ^2) value =33.268, df =12, p=0.001, Phi=0.437, Cramer's V=0.252)

Perceptions and Expectations on Skills Gap among Managers in SSMFs

Technical skills

The findings in Table 5 indicate that technical skills had overall mean scores of 3.2857 for perceptions and 3.9719 for expectations, meaning that employers had higher expectations on employees having adequate relevant skills required for the job than the real situation whereas the skills possessed by employees do not meet employers' expectations. The findings in detailed manner show that employers' perceptions on employees' skills were less than the expectations in all aspects under the study, for computer and ICT related skills [perceived mean of 3.0286 < expected mean of 3.6252], for accurate weighing and ability to make computations [perceived mean of 3.2800 < expected mean of 3.8256], for familiarity with large scale production equipment and techniques [perceived mean of 3.3029 < expected mean of 3.9234], for ability to keep up to date with technological innovations [perceived mean of 3.4400 < expected mean of 4.2637] and about sales and marketing skills [perceived mean of 3.3771 < expected mean of 4.2213]. These findings on detailed basis suggest that employees in the labour market failure to meet employers' expectations in all aspects related to technical skills, posing difficulty for employers to meet the desired goal of raising firms' performance. These findings show agreement with those in Munishi (2016) which found that graduates in the labour market demonstrated incompetencies to perform jobs as the result of higher education curricula being not effective, trainers being not competent, inadequacy of stress on soft skills and little is being done on career guidance.

Table 5. Perceived and expected skills among managers in SSMFs (n = 175)

Skills Gap	Perceived Mean (P)	Expected Mean (E)
Technical skills		
Computer and ICT-related skills	3.0286	3.6254
Accurate weighing and ability to make computations	3.2800	3.8256
Familiarity with large scale production equipment and techniques	3.3029	3.9234
Ability to keep up to date with technological innovations	3.4400	4.2637
Sales and marketing skills	3.3771	4.2213
Overall mean score	3.2857	3.9719
Communication skills		
Ability to communicate effectively	3.6457	4.2672
Ability to comprehend written instructions	3.7029	4.0146
Overall mean score	3.6743	4.1409
Problem solving skills		
Understanding and complying with quality assurance practices	3.4971	4.3671
Time management skills	3.3371	4.2996
Ability to be cross trained in numerous functions	3.5257	4.4920
Ability to think on their feet and troubleshoot small problems	3.3600	4.1416
Understanding and complying with health and safety standards	4.1886	4.4815
Overall mean score	3.5817	4.3564
Interpersonal skills		
Mindfulness and attention when operating machinery	3.6971	4.5216
Customer-oriented skills to boost enterprise image	3.7657	4.8237
Overall mean scores	3.7314	4.6727
Decision making skills		
Ability to assess and initiate things independently	3.2457	4.4352
Strong work ethic and organizational skills	3.4514	3.9635
Overall mean score	3.3486	4.1994

Communication skills

The findings as summarized in Table 5 indicate that the overall mean scores for communication skills was 3.6743 for perceived skills possessed by labour force and 4.1409 for employers' expectations about employees having required skills for the job. These findings imply show existence of mismatch between skills possessed by work force in the labour market and expectations of employers whereas employers' expectations are higher than the reality. The findings further entail that the perceived mean for ability to communicate effectively was 3.6457 as compared to 4.2672 and about ability to comprehend written instructions being 3.7029 and 4.0146 for perceptions and expectations. These findings are coherent to those of Munishi (2016) which established existence of knowledge gap in terms of soft skills including communication among graduates in the labour market in Tanzania.

Problem solving skills

The findings presented in Table 5 indicate overall mean scores of 3.5817 and 4.3564 for employers' perceptions and expectations respectively regarding to possession of problem-solving skills by employees in SSMFs, meaning that employers' expectations on problem solving skills possessed by employees in SSMFs were not met. The situation was found to be the same for all attributes under this variable, for understanding and complying with quality assurance practices [perceive mean = 3.4971, expected mean = 4.3671], time management skills [perceived mean = 3.3371, expected mean = 4.2996], ability to be cross trained in numerous functions [perceived mean = 3.5257, expected mean = 4.492], ability to think on their feet and troubleshoot small problems [perceived mean = 3.3600, expected mean = 4.1416] and understanding and complying with health and safety standards [perceived mean = 4.1886, expected mean = 4.4815]. The findings disclose that employees in SSMFs were perceived by employers to have limited skills concerning compliance with quality assurance practices, time management, mastering multitasks, critical thinking in having new alternatives in solving problems and compliance with health and safety standards. Furthermore, the findings disclose that if employees operate the way employers perceive them, this makes difficult for firms to achieve the intended goal of improved performance. These findings are similar to those of Adula *et al.* (2023) that established that problem solving skills and employees' performance had positive and significant relationship, interpreted that firms' management should strive to equip employees with problem solving skills.

Interpersonal skills

The findings in Table 5 show that the overall mean scores were 3.7314 and 4.6727 for perception and expectation respectively, bringing interpretation that employers' expectations on interpersonal skills possessed by employees in SSMFs were unmet, this suggests underperformance in the sector. Likewise, all attributes under this variable exhibited similar results as for employees having mindfulness and attention when operating machinery [perceived mean = 3.6971, expected mean = 4.5216] and customer-oriented skills to boost enterprise image [perceived mean = 3.7657, expected mean = 4.8237]. These findings tell that employees with limited mindfulness and attention during machine operation and customer oriented will hardly produce desired output, consequently the firm will suffer from poor customer retention and performance. These findings show similarity with those of Adula *et al.* (2023) which found that interpersonal skills and employees' performance were related to each other and the former formed employees' commitment that predicted firms' performance continuity.

Decision making skills

Table 5 summarizes that the overall mean scores for decision making skills were 3.3486 and 4.1994 for employers' perceptions and expectations respectively, meaning that employers' expectations regarding employees having decision making skills were unmet. Similar findings were also exhibited by all aspects included in the study, employees having ability to assess and initiate things independently [perceived mean = 3.2457, expected mean = 4.4352] and strong work ethic and organizational skills [perceived mean = 3.4514, expected mean = 3.9635]. These findings hint at employees

having limited skills required in making various decisions at workplace, as the result, firms' performance become jeopardized. These findings demonstrate resemblance with those of Mohd and Bulengela (2024) found that decision making skills are important for staff performance in Tanzania.

Skills gap

Generally, the findings in Table 6 indicate skills gap as denoted by an overall $P - E$ of -0.7302 , connoting that in manufacturing firms skills gap exist. These findings show similarity with those of Shivaramu *et al.* (2019) which identified existence of a negative difference between perceived and expected skills, connoting existence of skills gap.

Table 6. Skills gap

Variables/skills	Perceived mean (P)	Expected mean (E)	$P - E$ (Gap)	Ranking
Technical	3.2857	3.9719	-0.6862	4
Communication	3.6743	4.1409	-0.3979	5
Problem solving	3.5817	4.3564	-0.7747	3
Interpersonal	3.7314	4.6727	-0.9413	1
Decision making	3.3486	4.1994	-0.8508	2
Overall Skills Gap			-0.7302	

The findings in Table 6 further show that interpersonal skills were the first ranked skills gap [$P - E = -0.9413$] which was greater than the overall skills gap of -0.7302 , entailing that workforce in manufacturing firms are facing difficulties to interact with different business stakeholders including customers, meaning that, to realize intended business performance is difficult unless interaction between workforce and business stakeholders is maximized. These findings match with those presented in the NACTE (2020) which described that customer care which is one of interpersonal skills gaps was among skills gap confronting employees at workplaces in Tanzania.

The findings in Table 6 further present that decision making was second ranked skills gap with $P - E = -0.8508$ which was greater than the overall skill gap of -0.7302 , entailing that most of workforce in manufacturing firms are facing decision making skill gap. If workforce is unable to make decision, then it is difficult for the manufacturing firms to realize intended performance. These findings are congruent to those of Fissuh *et al.* (2022) which establish that skills for a specific job, in this study similar to decision making were one of the skills gaps at workplace in Canada.

In regard to problem solving skills, the findings in Table 6 were the third ranked skills gap [$P - E = -0.7747$] which was greater than skills gap of -0.7302 , with depiction that workforce in manufacturing firms hardly solve problems that emerge at workplace, as the result, reaching desired performance is difficult. These findings show close similarity with those of Fissuh *et al.* (2022) which earmarked that problem solving related skills were one of the skills gaps among workforce in Canada. The findings also match closely with those of NACTE (2020) which explained that problem solving was one of the skills gaps faced labour force in the job market in Tanzania.

Moreover, though the findings on technical skills gap in Table 6 [$P - E = -0.6862$] was below the overall skills gap of -0.7302 but still skills gap existed, meaning that without closing such a gap, manufacturing firms will hardly attain intended goals. These findings indicate close resemblance with those of Fissuh *et al.* (2022) which indicated existence of technical skill gap among employees at workplace in Canada.

Finally, though the findings on communication skills gap in Table 6 the findings in Table 2 [$P - E = -0.3979$] was below the overall skills gap and was the last ranked skills gap, meaning existence of the skills gap. This means that, for manufacturing firms to realize intended performance such skills gap needs to be closed. These findings indicate close similarity with those of NACTE (2020) which indicated existence of communication skills gap in the labour market in Tanzania.

Determinants of Skills gap for SSMFs' employees

The findings in Table 7 show that manufacturing firms are not consulted by education institution during development, revision or implementation of curricula [Mean = 4.4457, ranking 1], meaning that collaboration between manufacturing firms and education institutions should be enhanced for correctly understanding needs of the industry in terms of skills required and design appropriate curricula to close identified gaps. These findings are in synchronization with those of NACTE (2020) which established that one of the perceived reasons for skills gap among employees in Tanzania was a lot of theories being taught with little training on practical aspects in education system, this might have emanated from limited involvement of industry by education institutions.

Table 7. Determinants of skills gap for SSMFs' employees (n = 175)

Variables	Mean	Ranking
Inadequate budget for training and skill development	3.9143	N/A
Difficult for companies to hire the right people	3.7543	N/A
Insufficient funds to pay sufficiently skilled workers	4.1200	4
Consuming resources in training and skill development	3.8343	N/A
Inadequate vocational training in the community	4.4057	2
Inadequate labor supply to the market	3.9486	N/A
Manufacturing firms not consulted by education institutions	4.4457	1
Inadequate schools for technical education and training	4.1600	3
Consider education level as a significant factor in hiring	3.8914	N/A
Inadequate internship among manufacturing enterprise	3.9486	N/A
Overall mean score	4.0423	

The findings further in Table 7 depict that inadequate vocational training in the community was among the determining factor for skills gap for employees in small scale manufacturing firms [Mean = 4.40587, ranking 2], informing that employers perceive employees' skills gap to be caused by limited training on vocational aspects. These findings match in the same way as those of NACTE (2020) in the aspects limited integration of theories and practices in which vocational training are rooted from.

Table 7 also reports that inadequacy of technical education and training [Mean = 4.1600, ranking 3) was pronounced as one of the determining factors for skills gap among small scale manufacturing firms' workforce in Tanzania, expressing that shortage of technical education and training limit performance-based outcomes among firms engaged in small scale manufacturing. These findings show similarity with those of NACTE (2020) that presented that limited vocational education programmes is one of the causes of existing skills gap in the labour market.

Moreover, Table 7 summarizes that insufficient fund to sufficiently pay skilled workers [Mean = 4.1200, ranking 4] was pointed out as among of determining factors for the existing skills gap in Tanzanian labour market, bringing an interpretation that employers fail to remunerate equitably employees due to insufficient fund. These findings are in synergy with those of NACTE (2020) which exhibited that sometimes employers were unable to recruit qualified and well trained and professionals due to demand of high pay rates.

Empirical Results

Binary logistic regression tests

Table 8. Effect of skills Gap on performance of SSMFs

Variables	B	S.E.	Sig.	Exp (B)
Technical skills gap (index)	-0.654	0.476	0.004	0.240
Communication skills gap (index)	-0.326	0.318	0.002	0.596
Problem solving skills gap (index)	-0.714	0.492	0.025	0.626
Interpersonal skills gap (index)	-0.826	0.562	0.000	0.206
Decision making skills gap (index)	-0.754	0.492	0.000	0.228
Sex (dummy)	0.762	0.526	0.142	2.192
Age (years)	0.029	0.028	0.662	1.029
Constant	-0.623	1.702	0.726	0.582
Omnibus test - Chi-square	54.464(6) (p=0.000)			
Hosmer and Lemeshow $-\chi^2$	8.342(8) (p=0.514)			
Cox & Snell R ²	0.281			
Nagelkerke R ²	0.427			
-2 Log Likelihood	124.728			

Dependent variable: Performance of SSMFs (1= increased, 0= otherwise)

As determined by Chi-square in the omnibus test, the overall model fit (Table 8) from the logit was significant statistically ($p = 0.000$). This suggests that the skills gap that brings about effect to small-scale manufacturing firms' performance were anticipated by the model. Additionally, the Cox & Snell R² and Nagelkerke R² findings were 0.281 and 0.427 correspondingly, showing that predictors included in the model clarified 28.1% and 42.7% of the variance in the performance of small-scale manufacturing firms. The

dependent variable's degree of variation described by the model is indicated by the values of the Nagelkerke R^2 and Cox & Snell R^2 , which vary starting from 0 to 1. According to statistical explanation as presented by Pallant (2016), the values of Cox & Snell R^2 and Nagelkerke R^2 are not as actual as in the multiple linear regression results which are actual values of R^2 .

Binary logistic regression results

Technical skills gap

The summary of findings in Table 8 indicates negative coefficient of employees' technical skills gap (-0.654) that relate with the performance of SSMFs, and it was negative and significant statistically ($p = 0.004$), inferring that a unit increase in technical skills gap will produce 65.4% decline in the performance of SSMFs, meaning that if technical skills gap is closed, there is high likelihood for improving firms' performance. These findings agree with those of Robert and Mori (2024) which came up with evidence that technical skills were important for firms' performance in Tanzania, meaning that firms are required to ensure that employees are well trained on technical aspects which are in line with the firms' operations. Similar findings were found in Adula *et al.* (2023) which demonstrated that technical skills were required in order to improve employees' performance in Ethiopia. These findings further are in line with the Resource Based Theory that pinpoints that human capital in terms of capability is crucial for firms' performance as internal resource.

Communication skills gap

The summary of findings in Table 8 shows that the coefficient of communication skills gap was negative (-0.326) and significant statistically ($p = 0.002$) in relation to the performance of SSMFs, deducing that changing a unit of communication skills gap led to a decrease of 32.6% of the performance of SSMFs. These findings inform that as communication skills gap enlarge, the performance of SSMFs diminishes, calling for collaborative efforts to minimize such skills gap. These findings agree with those of Robert and Mori (2024) which discovered the importance of prioritizing on communication skills when formulating training programmes for employees.

Problem solving skills gap

The findings in Table 8 indicate that the coefficient of problem solving skills gap was negative (-0.714) with statistical significance ($p = 0.025$) relationship with the performance of SSMFs, pointing out that raising problem solving skills gap will cause diminish of firms' performance by 71.4%. These findings provide information that is vital for firms to fight against enlargement of problem solving skills gap and come up with ways of intensifying employees' training geared towards equipping them with problem solving skills. These findings draw up close similarity with those of Adula *et al.* (2023) which demonstrated that problem solving skills are related to employees' performance in industries specialized in clothing and textiles in Ethiopia as their commitment was the alarm for business continuity. Interpretation of these findings further argument to the study's findings by pinpointing that if skills gap related to

problem solving enlarges, there is high likelihood of firm's performance to decrease and the vice versa also is true. These findings are in connection with the Resource Based Theory in a sense that human capital with relevant skills as one of internal resources form a crucial component for firms' performance.

Interpersonal skills gap

Table 8 presents a summary of the findings on interpersonal skills gap with a negative coefficient (-0.826) on firms' performance, drawing up an interpretation that any attempt to rise interpersonal skills gap will cause a decline by 82.62% of firms' performance. These findings provide close connection with those of Adula *et al.* (2023) which determined that interpersonal skills and employees' performance in Ethiopia' clothing and textile industry were related to each other, giving interpretation that a lot of initiatives and efforts should be invested by firms' management to ensure interpersonal skills gap is closed or kept minimal for the sake of improving employees' performance.

Decision making skills

The findings in Table 8 indicate negative coefficient (-0.754) of decision making skills with a significant statistically ($p = 0.000$) effect on firms' performance, providing an implication that any unit rise in decision making skills gap will bring about 75.4% reduction of firms' performance. These findings are reinforced with those of Mohd and Bulengela (2024) which recognized that decision making skills was one of the skills required in improvement of staff performance in Tanzania. These findings bring about an interpretation that firms' management should proactively enhance staff decision making skills through continuous training programmes.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The research findings enable the conclusion to be made that skills gap among managers in numerous areas including technical, communication, problem solving, interpersonal and decision making as they were represented by a negative overall mean score that was used to measure skills gap in this research. Such negative overall mean score shows that managers in the SSMFs require several training programmes that will help to close the identified skills gap and improve firms' performance. The findings further enabled to conclude that manufacturing firms not consulted by education institutions, inadequate vocational training in the community, inadequate schools for technical education and training and insufficient funds to pay sufficiently skilled workers were identified as determinants of the established skills gap. This means that, if the identified determinants of skills gap are well addressed, the identified skills gap are probable to be closed and consequently improve firms' performance. Further, the study further concludes that identified skills gap including technical, communication, problem solving, interpersonal and decision making affect negatively the performance of employees in SSMFs. This means that when skills gap increases the performance of SSMFs decrease. The findings of this research provide contribution to the Resource Based Theory in a way stresses that despite huge

investment made by manufacturing firms in terms of financial, physical and technological resources, parallel investment should be undertaken in the development of human capital which is pivotal in management of other resources to ensure productivity is enhanced.

Recommendations

The recommendations are made to policymakers including VETA, SIDO, and the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology (MoEST) to collectively to ensure that adequate vocational training is extended to reach the wider community by establishing vocational training institutions to every district that will be closer to community members. Further, participatory reform of education curricula is required that involve consultation of manufacturing firms to enable identification of the required skills in the labour market and include them in the curricula. Such curricula reforms should prioritize on vocational education, quality standards and procedures that will enable graduates from training institutions to acquire the required competencies.

The recommendations further are made to the private sector and other development partners such as ILO, UNIDO and others to collectively support capacity building to owners of SSMFs and their employees to bridge the existing skills gap that will help in future to have well skilled labour that can deliver to meet or exceed firms' expectations.

The recommendations also are made to owners of SSMFs to be ready to set adequate budgets for training employees to bridge the existing skills gap and also be ready to pay sufficiently employees as the strategy for improving employees' morale and retention, that together become the means for improved firms' performance.

Limitations and areas for future research

The research was limited to Mwanza and Dar es Salaam cities without considering other cities, this limited generalization of findings. The research also was confined in only manufacturing industry and ignoring other industries, this also formed limitation in generalization of findings. Further, the study used only quantitative data that also formed the limitation for this research. Additionally, the study was limited to the use of cross-sectional research design due to its cost effectiveness and efficiency. From the identified limitations, in future it is recommended that similar research be carried in more than two cities and also consider inclusion of rural setting for comparative analysis. Further, it is recommended that more than one industry should be considered for comparative analysis and use of both quantitative and qualitative data to enrich study findings should be considered for future study. The recommendation is also made for future research to consider use of longitudinal research design with the aim of tracking developmental changes in skills gap over time.

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